

THE ROLE OF THE PENITENTIARY SYSTEM IN THE RESOCIALIZATION OF PERSONS RELEASED FROM CORRECTIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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The role of the penitentiary system in the social adaptation of persons released from correctional institutions is very great. Before discussing its important aspect, it is appropriate to briefly explain its content.

The penitentiary system, which is one of the main concepts in the field of criminal-executive law, is a system that covers actions related to the execution of punishment imposed on persons found guilty by the court of committing a certain act. Scientists have given different definitions to this concept, including the definition of N. Salaev, which comprehensively revealed the essence of the penitentiary system: “Penitentiary system - a system that includes the educational, moral, pedagogical, psychological, political, legal, socio-economic and other areas of activity of state bodies and institutions for the implementation of criminal penalties and other measures of criminal law aimed at correcting and resocialization of convicts”[1, p.16].

Therefore, the penitentiary system includes not only the execution of prescribed punishments, but also the implementation of measures aimed at the moral correction of prisoners. Therefore, the resocialization of convicts should begin while they are serving their sentence. Their support after release should facilitate a smooth transition from prison to society, build on the successes achieved in prison through treatment and education programs, and continue until successful reintegration is completed [2, pp. 120-129]. These ideas are also enshrined in the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (the Nelson Mandela Rules): “It is desirable to adopt the necessary measures to ensure the prisoner’s gradual adaptation to society before the end of his sentence.” [3, Rule 87] Furthermore, the purpose of imprisonment or similar deprivation of liberty is, above all, to protect society from crime and to reduce recidivism. These purposes can only be achieved if the period of deprivation of liberty is used, so far as possible, to ensure

the reintegration of such persons into society upon release and to lead a law-abiding and independent life... [4, Rule 4]

According to Article 42 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the purpose of punishment is to correct the morality of the convicted person, prevent him from continuing his criminal activity, and also prevent the convicted person, like other persons, from committing a new crime. Therefore, when executing punishments, the issue of moral correction of convicted persons should be the most important, since the possibility of moral correction and education of convicted persons is limited only by depriving them of certain rights or imposing certain duties on them. Unfortunately, today the main attention of the penitentiary institutions of our country is focused on the execution of punishments.

The Criminal Executive Codes of the Republics of Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan, which are neighboring countries, define the issues of moral correction of prisoners and their resocialization, and the issue of their combination with resocialization is presented as a principle [5, Articles 14, 5 respectively], that is, the execution of punishment and criminal-legal measures must comprehensively support socio-psychological and pedagogical instruments aimed at the correction and resocialization of prisoners [6, Article 14].

Since the main legal basis for the execution of punishments is the Criminal Executive Code, then the issues related to the educational influence and education of convicts in this Code are covered in Chapters 14-15 of the Criminal Executive Code, and from these chapters it consists of only six substances (4 and 2 respectively). Since the main purpose of applying criminal punishment is the education of the convict, then the main attention should be paid to the norms aimed at his educational situation.

APPENDIX 19 to the internal regulations of the institutions of deprivation of liberty of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the approximate daily routine of prisoners, according to which time spent in the toilet, washing and physical education, bed rest, morning and evening registration, breakfast, lunch, dinner, meeting and return time, working hours, free time, general secondary and vocational education, attendance of social and cultural events, preparation for sleep and sleep time are provided. , in which 1 hour is allocated for the prisoner's free time and 1 hour for participation in general secondary and vocational education, social and cultural events according to the schedule. This is very little time for the re-education of convicts.

According to the Criminal-executive Code of the Kyrgyz Republic, correction and socialization of prisoners, the desire of prisoners to engage in socially useful activities, conscientious attitude to work, the requirements of the law and other norms of behavior accepted in society are determined that it is aimed at forming and strengthening compliance with the rules of behavior, raising the educational and cultural level, instilling family values, awareness of the illegality of the crime committed and taking measures to compensate for the damage caused by the crime, participation in rehabilitation programs. Public and charitable organizations, relatives of prisoners and other persons who have a positive influence on their behavior are voluntarily involved in educational influence, and social adaptation and psychological work with prisoners are one of the main tasks of correction. work and life are organized.

Therefore, it is very important to conduct educational and preventive work with convicts while serving their sentences in places of imprisonment, to develop various programs aimed at their resocialization. The main goal of social reintegration programs is to provide offenders with the support and supervision they may need so that they can give up crime, successfully reintegrate into society and prevent recidivism. In general, there are three main categories of social reintegration programs: prison rehabilitation programs, post-release reintegration and care programs and out-of-community programs. If these measures are not implemented, the scale of problems that released prisoners may face will increase and the likelihood of reoffending will increase.

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